

GenInk: A Framework for Tattoo Image Synthesis

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Abstract—Tattoos have long been used as complementary information to support the identification of subjects in forensic investigations. This is mainly due to their discriminative patterns and designs, which are valuable in identifying individuals. However, privacy concerns surrounding the collection of real tattoo databases have hampered the development of robust tattoo recognition systems in the past. With recent advances in generative neural networks, it is possible to generate synthetic tattoos, opening up new research directions. In this paper, we propose GenInk, a framework for the generation of synthetic tattoos based on an existing multimodal generative model. To the best of our knowledge, GenInk enables the generation of the first fully synthetic tattoo database that can be used for training tattoo recognition. Experimental evaluations on real tattoo databases show promising results, i.e., rank-1 identification rates above 95%, when using the proposed synthetic database for training in an identification task.

Index Terms—Tattoo retrieval, synthetic data, stable diffusion models, image synthesis, and soft-biometrics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tattoos have long been recognised as an important form of self-expression and cultural art, practised for centuries in various societies [1]. In recent years, the role of tattoos has expanded beyond mere body art to become a form of soft biometrics that helps law enforcement agencies identify wanted criminals and missing persons [2]. In contrast to other biometric characteristics, e.g. fingerprints and faces, tattoos cannot be used to directly establish the identity of a subject. However, tattoos, unlike other soft biometrics, such as gender, age or race, contain more discriminative information to support the subject identification and are a useful indicator to track members of a criminal gang or organisation [3]. The above reasons have led forensic investigators to develop automated image-based tattoo retrieval techniques that allow, e.g., to retrieve from a tattoo image database a candidate list of tattooed subjects with similar tattoo patterns [4]. The retrieved images in the candidate list may contain other types of (soft) biometric characteristics (e.g., the hand or skin colour) that allow for definitive identification of the targeted suspect.

Regarding tattoo retrieval, NIST’s Tatt-C and Tatt-E challenges developed some of the former automatic tattoo detection and identification systems for real forensic applications [5]. Old practices for tattoo image retrieval were based on keyword or metadata matching [6]. Despite their effectiveness, keyword-based systems had several limitations, namely an insufficient vocabulary to describe different tattoo patterns

Fig. 1: Examples of the fully synthetic GenInk tattoo database generated by the proposed pipeline.

and inconsistent labels, which led to the development of handcrafted and deep learning techniques [7]–[9].

At present, gaining the necessary data to train and test tattoo retrieval algorithms is still a difficult task. That is, machine learning-based systems face considerable challenges, primarily due to their reliance on databases containing real-world images. The collection of tattooed images is often hampered by privacy concerns, ethical considerations, and legal restrictions, leading to a scarcity of comprehensive databases¹. This lack of publicly available tattoo datasets (see Tab. I) has hindered the development of effective tattoo-retrieval systems. The databases in Tab. I are mostly limited to a few variations in cultural diversity, image quality and also variety and quality of drawing, which leads to retrieval systems showing little generalisation in retrieving unseen data.

Advances in multimodal deep generative networks that integrate information from diverse sources (e.g. text, images, audio) have transformed creative fields, including tattoo design. Multimodal generative models allow tattoo artists to create designs that were previously unimaginable. Technologies such as diffusion models and generative adversarial networks (GANs) improve the synthesis of tattoo images, overcoming

¹https://news.sophos.com/en-us/2020/03/19/nist-shared-dataset-of-tattoos-thats-been-used-to-identify-prisoners/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

TABLE I: Overview of available tattoo databases.

Database	#Categories	#Samples	Public	Fully Synthetic
HDA-STD [10]	–	5,500	Yes	✗
WebTattoo [6]	400*	1,400	Yes	✗
DeMSI [11]	–	890	Yes	✗
Tatt-C [3]	157†	215	No	✗
BIVTatt [12]	210	4,200	Yes	✗
PinTatt [12]	160	454	No	✗
NTU-Tattoo-V1 [13]	–	10,000	Yes	✗
TattTRN-DB [14]	571	28,550	Yes	✗
GenInk (this work)	565	27,651	Yes	✓

* Publicly available training set.

† Number of categories reported for the identification case.

the limitations of traditional databases.

In this paper, we present a multimodal generative model-based tattoo image generation framework together with a realistic and fully synthetic tattoo image database referred to as GenInk. The synthetic database contains 565 different tattoo categories with at least 36 images each. It is demonstrated that the introduced GenInk database is suitable for training state-of-the-art tattoo retrieval systems.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Related work is summarised in Sect. II. In Sect. III, GenInk is described. The experimental setup is summarized in Sect. IV. Experimental results including a benchmark of the proposed database against non-fully synthetic images are presented in Sect V. Conclusions and future work directions are finally summarised in Sect. VI.

II. RELATED WORK

Biometric identification technologies have been widely used in law enforcement to identify suspects or missing persons, making tattoo recognition (retrieval) a relevant investigation area. Despite the progress registered by the NIST Tatt-C and Tatt-E challenges for generalisable tattoo-retrieval systems, the lack of large-scale tattoo databases has hindered their development [5]. Tab. I shows an overview of existing tattoo databases. Note that most datasets have a limited number of categories and samples (e.g., BIVTatt [12] and PinTatt [12]), and some of them are not public (e.g., Tatt-C [3] and PinTatt [12]). Recently, Gonzalez-Soler *et al.* [14] proposed a tattoo retrieval scheme (TattTRN) together with a semi-synthetic database that included 28,550 images generated from the combination of 571 different artificial tattoo templates and real body parts. This database was tested on real-world datasets, such as BIVTatt [12] and WebTattoo [6], showing promising results. The adoption of semi-synthetic data has driven significant advances in the development of robust tattoo recognition systems, setting new benchmarks in both technical performance and ethical data management [10], [14], [15].

In parallel to the advancements in tattoo recognition, the development of generative networks for art generation (including tattoos) has seen significant innovations, primarily driven by the evolution of GANs and their variations [16], [17], leading up to more sophisticated diffusion models [18], [19]. GANs allow the generation of artwork and designs from simple descriptions (e.g., using StyleGAN family [20]). Recent

Fig. 2: Conceptual overview of the proposed GenInk tattoo image synthesis pipeline, in which a generator based on stable diffusion models is fed with text prompts consisting of human-defined tattoo categories and other characteristics.

approaches have focused more on the use of diffusion models (e.g., Latent Diffusion Models (LDM) [18], Midjourney [21], SDXL [22], DALL-E 3 [23]) due to the high image quality of the samples and their large latent space enabling larger variation. By leveraging the power of these generative models, the limitations of traditional tattoo databases can be mitigated. That is, large-scale synthetic databases pave the way for training more accurate and reliable tattoo retrieval systems.

III. TATTOO IMAGE SYNTHESIS

According to Makrushin *et al.* [24], biometric data synthesis must comply with a number of general requirements, including realistic appearance, sufficiently high image resolution, data anonymity and diversity/uniqueness, among others. Currently, the existing tattoo databases in Tab. I that attempt to simulate synthetic data do not comply with several of the above requirements. The TattTRN-DB database [14] combines, for example, real human back and chest images with synthetic tattoo templates to generate semi-synthetic biometric data. According to [14], real images of the human body are only limited to chest and back samples and reflect mostly light skin tones, resulting in a lack of diversity in the images. The use of real images that were proposed for the detection of permanent pigmented or vascular skin marks could also share sensitive data in the new data generated [25]–[27].

To overcome the above limitations, we propose a new fully synthetic tattoo database. Fig. 2 shows the pipeline for tattoo image synthesis named GenInk. The proposed scheme consists mainly of two components: *i*) the creation of text prompts that are diverse in terms of the number of categories or classes, areas of the human body for placement as well as skin characteristics, and *ii*) the generation of realistic tattoo images from the aforementioned text prompts. To guarantee a high degree of diversity, the text prompts in the first module follow the following structured format:

A **Category** tattoo on the **Body placement** of a person with a **Skin characteristic** skin tone,

Fig. 3: Testing databases used in the experiments.

where **Body placement** includes common body parts, such as shoulder, arm, neck, back, leg and chest, and **Skin characteristic** varies from light to dark. To ensure a sufficient number of tattoo categories, we manually created up to 565 conceptual classes e.g., animals, tribals, landscapes, flowers, texts, etc.

To properly generate realistic image, we investigated different generative networks (e.g., Midjourney [21] and DALL-E 3 [23])) and selected three popular stable diffusion models in the second component, which satisfy the general requirements for image synthesis [24]: LDM [18], SDXL-Base [22], SDXL-Turbo [22]. The former is the classical LDM proposed by Rombach *et al.* [18] while the latter two involve an ensemble of expert pipelines for latent diffusion. In essence, diffusion models are parametrised Markov chain-based approaches that are trained by variational inference to produce samples corresponding to the data after a finite amount of time [28]. In our work, only the LDM generator is employed. Therefore, the initial Gaussian noise z_T is denoised by applying T encoder-decoder submodules based on UNet [29] and the denoised z_0 latent representation is finally transformed to the pixel space. During image synthesis, a text prompt that varies according to tattoo categories, body location and skin characteristics enables the networks' cross-attention mechanism [30]. SDXL-Turbo is based on a novel training method called Adversarial Diffusion Distillation (ADD) [31], which makes it possible to generate images in a single step with unprecedented quality, reducing the number of steps required from 50 to just one. Fig. 1 shows examples of images generated using our pipeline.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup focuses on evaluating the utility of the generated images as training for tattoo-retrieval systems. Thus, they can successfully retrieve real tattooed images. The experiments are organised in three phases. Phase 1 acts as a proof of concept and aims to analyse the utility of the generated samples for the training of tattoo recognition systems. Phase 2 expands the text prompts by adding more categories of tattoos, as well as skin characteristics. To further improve the performance of the retrieval methods, different data enhancements are applied to the synthetic samples in

phase 3. In our work, a variety of data augmentation is used, including random flipping, rotation, brightness and contrast adjustment, and blurring. To establish a fair benchmark against the baseline systems, data augmentation in Phase 3 is also applied to the semi-synthetic database (TattTRN-DB) in [14] that is used for the training of baseline schemes.

In all experiments, we followed a cross-database protocol in [14] where the proposed database is used to train the systems and the real ones to evaluate performance. We randomly sample 2 images per identity (i.e. one for biometric registration and the other as an identification transaction) in the test set and run a closed-set evaluation as in [14]. The procedure is repeated 10 times and the mean identification rates (IR) together with the standard deviation are reported as Cumulative Matching Characteristic (CMC) curves [32]. The identification performance of the systems is also evaluated for an open-set scenario in terms of False Negative Identification Rates (FNIR) and False Positive Identification Rates (FPIR), and their values are provided as Detection Error Trade-Off (DET) curves [32]. For open-set identification, the identity set of the test set is randomly divided into 10 subsets and 10% of the identities are used as biometric transactions and the remaining 90% for biometric enrolment in each case.

A. Implementation Details

Baseline systems (i.e., EfficientNetv2 [33] and SwinTransformer (Swin) [34]), which showed reliable performance for the tattoo retrieval task in [14] were implemented and trained utilising a Nvidia A100 Tensor Core GPU with 40 GB of GPU Memory over the proposed database. The image size was set to 224×224 . The networks were initialised with their pre-trained weights on ImageNet [35] and trained for 100 epochs using the Adam optimiser with a learning rate of $1e-5$ and weight decay of 0.95. A batch size of 32 images is also set for training. Following to [14], baseline systems are optimised using the ArcFace loss [36] for different angular margin parameters (0.1 and 0.5) to have two different embedding sizes (256 and 512).

For the implementation of the above diffusion models, we use the Diffusers library in Hugging Face² with the next pre-trained weights: `stable-diffusion-v1-5` for LDM [18], `stable-diffusion-xl-base-1.0` for SDXL-Base [22], and `sdxl-turbo` for SDXL-Turbo [22]. To speed up inference and save memory, all model weights were set to `float16`. Thus, the generation takes between 4 and 33 seconds per image depending on the model.

B. Testing Databases

We selected the two publicly available databases in Tab. I that provide tattoo category labels and different tattoo patterns by category, i.e., WebTattoo [6] and BIVTatt [12] to evaluate the tattoo-retrieval systems. WebTattoo [6] consists of some 300,000 samples from 600 different tattoo categories collected from the Internet. In our work, we only used the training set of 1,400 images of 400 tattoo types that were made

²<https://huggingface.co/>

TABLE II: Closed-set identification performance of different tattoo-retrieval systems in terms of IRs (%) at Rank-1 on real images in WebTattoo [6] and BiVTatt [12]. The best performance per database is highlighted in bold.

P	Database	WebTattoo				BiVTatt			
		m	0.1		0.5		0.1		0.5
	K	256	512	256	512	256	512	256	512
Fully-synthetic GenInk Tattoo Database									
1	EfficientNet	73.14	74.10	66.31	67.30	83.52	84.28	78.30	79.18
	Swin	78.60	79.90	75.53	76.09	89.62	89.69	86.10	86.35
2	EfficientNet	72.53	76.41	52.14	63.22	84.15	89.37	63.33	71.13
	Swin	78.89	81.47	59.66	65.63	89.31	90.19	72.08	78.11
3	EfficientNet	76.51	77.74	45.11	67.15	90.25	89.18	60.44	77.30
	Swin	80.09	83.51	48.70	71.72	92.83	94.59	68.36	83.08
Semi-synthetic TattTRN-DB [14]									
-	EfficientNet	77.00	77.74	76.22	79.85	78.24	80.44	80.06	82.52
	Swin	78.85	81.01	82.06	82.75	80.50	85.41	83.96	85.60
3	EfficientNet	79.41	79.51	79.12	80.86	88.68	89.56	89.31	89.69
	Swin	81.84	83.05	80.42	81.97	90.06	91.38	90.00	92.33

available to the research community. BiVTatt [12] contains 210 real tattoo images and after applying 20 different types of transformations to the above images, the database finally consists of 4,200 samples. Following [14] 3,103 samples from 159 tattoo categories were used. Fig. 3 shows examples of testing databases.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Parameter Optimisation and Benchmarking

The utility of the proposed database for the above phases (P) is evaluated in the first experiment. Tab. II reports the retrieval performance for two systems in terms of IRs at Rank-1 for different parameter configurations. Note that the best performance in both databases is achieved for an angular margin (i.e., m) of 0.1 with an embedding size of 512 components when the retrieval pipelines are trained with our fully synthetic database; other K values do not correctly encode meaningful tattoo patterns and therefore the angular margin cannot properly separate feature embeddings in the latent space. Observe that the Swin-based scheme can retrieve the searched tattoo samples in the first entry of the candidate list with an accuracy of up to 83.51% for WebTattoo and 94.59% for BiVTatt. Phase 3, which expands the number of text tattoo categories and also applies data augmentation to the training samples, improves retrieval performance by at least 2% over the performance shown by the previous phases.

Compared to the results obtained by the same systems trained with the semi-synthetic TattTRN-DB database [14], our proposed database contributed positively to improving their performance in both cases. Swin-based pipeline trained with our fully synthetic database in phase 3 outperforms the same system trained with the database in [14] by 2.50 (without data augmentation as phase 3) and 0.46 (with data augmentation as phase 3) percentage points when the challenging WebTattoo database is evaluated (i.e., 83.51% vs. 81.01% vs. 83.05%). The performance gain can be even greater for BiVTatt, 94.59% vs. 85.60% vs. 92.33%. The results confirm that the fully

(a) Our fully-synthetic GenInk database.

(b) Semi-synthetic TattTRN-DB [14].

Fig. 4: Closed-set performance as CMC curves of the tattoo-retrieval systems trained either with our fully synthetic database or the TattTRN-DB for different rank values.

synthetic database contains more sample variability than those in [14], which contributes to improving the performance of the retrieval systems. Note some differences (e.g., image quality and realism) between the images in our GenInk database (Fig. 1) and those in TattTRN-DB [14]. While TattTRN images only show tattoos on the chest or back of the real subject, samples from our fully synthetic database are automatically blended in different body parts through text prompts.

B. Closed-set Performance

In forensic applications, investigators often analyse not only the first entry in a list of candidates to identify potential suspects. Fig. 4 reports, therefore, the retrieval performance as CMC curves of the above systems for the best parameter combination (i.e., $m = 0.1$, $K = 512$ and Phase 3) and compare them with the same systems for their best parameter settings. Note similar trends in most CMC curves for rank values greater than 1, i.e. the systems perform similarly on real data independent of the training database. However, looking more closely, we see that the Swin-based scheme with the proposed database grows faster (i.e., quickly reaches high IRs in the first ranks) than the same for TattTRN-DB. Furthermore, the Swin curves for our database appear narrower (smaller standard deviation) than those for TattTRN-DB. In this way, forensic experts do not need to exhaustively check the entire list of candidates to spot wanted perpetrators or missing persons.

C. Open-set Performance

In case there is potentially no reference in the enrolment database of the queried sample, the open-set performance as DET curves for both retrieval systems under their best

Fig. 5: Open-set performance as DET curves of the tattoo-retrieval systems trained either with our fully-synthetic GenInk database or the semi-synthetic TattTRN-DB.

parameter configuration is shown in Fig. 5. For this case, the systems trained with the semi-synthetic TattTRN-DB database slightly outperform the same pipelines trained with our GenInk database, i.e., EER values for TattTRN-DB are up to 2 percentage points lower than the ones reported by the proposed GenInk database. This means that our database makes systems more prone to false positives than TattTRN-DB. A potential solution would rely on including other attributes (e.g., image quality variation or furry skin) in the text prompts to allow retrieval networks to learn more robust features.

D. Tattoo Retrieval Examples

Fig. 6 shows some examples of candidate lists retrieved by the Swin-based system for different queried images on both testing databases. In line with the results of Tab. II, the scheme is able to retrieve with a high IR the correct reference image in rank-1 from the enrolled database for each sample searched in BIVTatt, even when the queried images have skewed distortions (e.g., second row in Fig. 6a). Note that changing the colour of the tattoo does not dramatically impact the system performance, reporting a similarity of up to 90% for two samples of the same tattoo with different colours (see first row in Fig. 6a). However, the change in skin colour combined with image distortions results in performance degradation: the rank-4 image in the second row of Fig. 6a reports only 30% similarity to its respective searched sample. The image

Fig. 6: Examples of candidate lists retrieved by Swin trained on the GenInk database.

quality degradation over time can also affect the system performance, leading to a low degree of similarity between two samples of the same tattoo (see first and second rows of Fig. 6b). For practical applications with large databases, this is a problem that will have to be addressed in the near future, as the number of false positives increases with the number of enrolled references [37]. We think that retrieval systems that include quality-aware loss functions (e.g., MagFace [38]), could potentially improve the erroneously retrieved samples. Low-quality images, which might even be difficult for a human being to analyse, could also benefit from a super-resolution approach, as mentioned in [14].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed a framework for leveraging existing generative multimodal models to generate synthetic tattoo images that can be used to train tattoo recognition systems. We generated the realistic and fully synthetic GenInk database containing tattoo images of up to 565 classes and 27,651 tattoo images. The generated synthetic database was used to train retrieval schemes whose performance was evaluated on real-world tattoo databases. Experimental results were compared with the semi-synthetic TattTRN-DB database, showing that the proposed GenInk database allowed systems to improve their performance by up to 4 percentage points in a closed-set scenario depending on the test database. One of the major advantages of our proposal is that it offers the possibility of generating large numbers of diverse images at minimal cost. GenInk can also be used to complement real tattoo databases for training systems and further enhance their performance.

Despite its advantages, there are some limitations. Although the synthetic dataset performed well overall, its performance was slightly inferior when tested in an open-set scenario with the WebTattoo database, which contains lower-quality images. This suggests that the synthetic generation process may need to be refined to improve the model's ability to generalise to different real-world datasets.

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